

11th International conference on Database Management Systems (DMS 2020)

November 21~22, 2020, Zurich, Switzerland

<https://cst2020.org/dms/index.html>

Call for Papers

11th International conference on Database Management Systems (DMS 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Database Management Systems. The goal of this conference is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Modern developments in this field and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to this conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Database management systems.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- 5G and Networks for Big Data
- Big Data Analytics and Social Media
- Big Data Applications, Bioinformatics, Multimedia etc
- Big Data Infrastructure and platform
- Big Data Management
- Big Data Mining
- Big Data Search and Mining
- Big Data Security, Privacy and Trust
- Big Data Techniques, models and algorithms
- Big Data Tools and systems
- Cloud and grid computing for Big Data
- Constraint Modelling and Processing
- Data and information Integration and Modelling
- Data and Information Networks
- Data and Information Privacy and Security
- Data and Information Quality
- Data and Information Semantics
- Data and Information Streams
- Data Management in Grid and P2P Systems
- Data Mining Algorithms
- Data Mining Applications
- Data Mining Foundations
- Data Mining Systems, Data Warehousing, OLAP
- Data Structures and Data Management Algorithms
- Database and Information System Architecture and Performance
- DB Systems & Applications
- Digital Libraries
- Distributed, Parallel, P2P and Grid-based Databases
- Electronic Commerce and Web Technologies
- Electronic Government and eParticipation
- Expert Systems and Decision Support Systems
- Expert Systems, Decision Support Systems and Applications
- Information Retrieval and Database Systems
- Information Systems
- Interoperability
- Knowledge Processing
- Knowledge Acquisition, discovery and Management
- Knowledge and Information Processing
- Knowledge Modelling
- Knowledge Processing
- Metadata Management
- Machine Learning and AI for Big Data
- Mobile Data and Information

- Multi-databases and Database Federation
- Multimedia, Object, Object Relational and Deductive Databases
- Pervasive Data and Information
- Process Modelling
- Process Support and Automation
- Query Processing and Optimization
- Semantic Web and Ontologies
- Sensor Data Management
- Statistical and Scientific Databases
- Temporal, Spatial, and High Dimensional Databases
- Trust, Privacy & Security in Digital Business
- User Interfaces to Databases and Information Systems
- Very Large Data Bases
- Workflow Management and Databases
- WWW and Databases
- XML and Databases

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **September 12, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **DMS 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journal.

- [International Journal of Database Management Systems \(IJDMS\)](#)
- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process \(IJDMP\)](#)
- [International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology \(IJCSIT\)](#) - INSPEC Indexed
- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : September 12, 2020**
- Authors Notification : October 05, 2020
- Registration & camera – Ready Paper Due : October 13, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: dms@cst2020.org (or) dmsconf@yahoo.com

Submission System

<https://cst2020.org/submission/index.php>